

A unifying finite strain modeling framework for anisotropic mixed-mode fracture in soft materials

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Abstract

Elastomers and composites made thereof have wide applications, e.g., in automobile, aerospace, and civil engineering. Predicting fracture in such materials is crucial for efficient design and optimum utilization. These materials are oftentimes hyperelastic and anisotropic in nature and in general subjected to mixed mode loading rather than merely pure modes. Soft biological tissues can also be considered anisotropic hyperelastic materials. Computational modeling helps in studying the role of different sources influencing mixed-mode fracture. A unifying thermodynamically consistent anisotropic phase field formulation for modeling the mixed-mode fracture of hyperelastic soft materials like elastomers, elastomeric fiber-reinforced composites, and soft biological tissues at finite strains is proposed and formulated. To model the mechanical response of anisotropic hyperelastic materials subjected to mixed-mode loading, a coupled Neo-Hookean model with orthotropic anisotropy is adopted considering volumetric-deviatoric *and* a tension-compression decomposition. For modeling the complex crack initiation and propagation, a phase field method based on a power law criterion is adopted by considering a single order parameter as the damage variable. This model is suitable for capturing the overall response of soft fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites as well as soft biological tissues. The proposed model is validated by conducting fracture tests on (a) silicone elastomers, (b) unidirectional fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites, (c) natural rubber reinforced with black carbon, and (d) brain tissue reinforced with axons. The results obtained are compared with experimental and numerical investigations from literature.

1 Introduction

Developing failure-resistant materials requires understanding failure in terms of fracture and/or damage, and predicting the behavior under different loading conditions. In materials like elastomers, their fiber-reinforced composites, and soft biological tissues, inherent inhomogeneity, and anisotropy coexist. These materials behave elastically when subjected to large deformations. The failure in certain anisotropic materials under large deformations is depicted in Figure 1.

At the microstructural level, fiber-reinforced composites (FRC) of elastomers like carbon-reinforced natural rubber as well as soft biological tissues consist of an isotropic soft matrix with reinforcements like fibers/axons, arranged at different orientations. Hyperelastic material models based on the definition of a strain energy function have been used in the analysis of materials subjected to finite deformations, e.g., rubber [1], synthetic elastomers [2, 3], and biological tissues [4]. The strain energy of such materials can be additively decomposed into distinct terms related to the isotropic matrix and anisotropic fiber families [5]. The constitutive law of these models can be written in terms of

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the deformation gradient tensor [6], invariants of the right Cauchy Green tensor [7], and principal stretches [8]. For considering the effect of anisotropy, additional invariants are considered as a function of fiber stretch [9]. Several material parameters are selected based on the chosen hyperelastic model [10]. At physiological loading rates, soft biological tissues tend to behave as incompressible or nearly incompressible. For modeling incompressibility, the decomposition of the deformation gradient into dilatational and volumetric contributions has been considered in the literature [11]. Also, an energy decomposition method that distinguishes tensile and compressive principal stretches has been proposed to enhance numerical stability [12]. Different isotropic and anisotropic strain energy functions have been proposed to describe the constitutive behavior of soft materials such as brain tissue [13, 14].

Figure 1: (a) Failure of fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites at laminate, ply, and intra-ply level [15], (b) Composite damage at different length scales [16], (c) Crack propagation in a carbon black-filled rubber [17], (d) Grey and white matter of the brain [18], (e) Illustration of the arrangement of the myelin sheath (black boundary) and the axon in cross-section (black dots: microtubules, grey dots: neurofilaments), and (f) Pure shear test and dent test of silicone rubber [19].

In (elastomeric) FRC's, the failure initiates with interfacial decohesion or fiber breakage, resulting in matrix cracking and leading to the ultimate failure of the material. To understand the complex failure phenomena in fiber-reinforced composites, anisotropic continuum damage models [20], nonlocal models [21, 22], finite fracture mechanics-based models [23], cohesive zone models [24, 25], phase field models [26], XFEM [27], and gradient-enhanced damage models [28] have been proposed in the literature. Soft biological tissues like the brain are arguably anisotropic in nature, e.g., due to the presence of collagen fibers dispersed in a soft matrix. Microstructure-based mechanical models which can capture the ultrasoft, heterogeneous nature of biological tissues need to be developed to predict the mechanical and failure response. Brain tissue is one of the most complex tissues in the human body, which is made up of white and gray matter of which the white matter is argued to be anisotropic [29, 30, 31] due to the presence of axons and the gray matter is considered to be isotropic [32, 33]. Therefore, the brainstem can be considered as a transversely isotropic material [34]. Budday et al. [29] recently summarized various challenges in testing and modeling brain tissue. To understand the influence of axonal orientation and relative stiffness of blood vessels to that of the surrounding tissue

in local brain injuries, a relation between the mechanical state at the tissue and cellular levels has been proposed [34]. The influence of mechanical forces at various rates, and of different magnitudes, on traumatic brain injury have been studied experimentally [35] and numerically [36]. Computational modeling of damage in a brain tissue reinforced with axons helps in understanding the effect of externally applied mechanical forces that influence susceptibility to injury.

Of all the existing computational models, phase field modeling (PFM) has proven to be efficient in capturing crack nucleation and tracking crack paths [37, 38]. PFM is based on the theoretical aspects of Griffith’s fracture criteria and the early works of Bourdin [39], Francfort and Marigo [40]. A sharp crack is regularized and represented by a scalar variable which is evaluated at each load step through an evolution equation in line with the displacement using a staggered approach [41]. The phase field approach can be adopted for modeling brittle fracture [42], ductile fracture [43], transient dynamic fracture [44], interfacial fracture [45], dynamic fracture [11], anisotropic fracture of composites [5], cubic materials [46], polycrystals [47], rocks [48], and rubbery polymers [8]. In laminated composites [26] and soft biological tissues [49], an anisotropic crack driving force based on the fiber direction was introduced, which has also been extended to large strain problems [50]. The coupled effect of the anisotropic elastic response and the anisotropic phase field evolution is considered in [51], and two distinct phase field variables for capturing direction-dependent fracture are adopted in [52]. The anisotropy is distinguished as weak or strong based on the reciprocal of the orientation-dependent fracture energy $G_c(\theta)$ [53]. The above-mentioned phase field models are based on weak anisotropy, where only the first-order gradient of the phase field has been considered, and are deemed sufficient for modeling fracture in biological tissues [54, 49], and composites reinforced with one/two fiber families [50]. For polycrystalline structures, thin sheets, and materials with cubic symmetry, zig-zag, or sawtooth-type crack patterns are observed [55, 56, 57]. Therefore, for such materials, strong anisotropy in terms of a fourth-order phase field approach needs to be considered [12, 51] which makes the finite element implementation complex. For modeling fracture using phase-field modeling in incompressible hyperelastic materials, both the energy decomposition and incompressibility need to be considered [58].

In this work, a unifying finite strain framework for modeling anisotropic mixed-mode fracture in soft materials is presented. In this new formulation, the anisotropic strain energy density function considers (i) a volumetric-deviatoric energy decomposition for modeling mixed-mode fracture similar to the one described in [59], *and* (ii) a tension-compression decomposition to avoid fracture under compression. Moreover, the anisotropic strain energy description is based on an exponential function similar to the one described in [7]. This allows us to model anisotropy in soft biological tissues. Finally, a mixed-mode critical energy release rate based on nonlinear interaction between two propagation modes (mode I and mode II) is considered from [60]. The proposed model thus unifies in a finite strain setting all the advantageous features adopted from various models. Taken together, the present work is different from the already available literature [7, 9] in the following aspects: it considers (i) a volumetric-deviatoric decomposition for modeling nearly incompressible behavior of materials, (ii) a fracture criterion based on the maximum positive strain energy to model the failure of anisotropic soft materials, and (iii) a mixed-mode fracture criterion based on a power law to model the fracture in materials like elastomers. The unified fracture model is validated by conducting mixed-mode fracture test on soft silicone elastomers. The obtained results are compared qualitatively, by plotting the damage profiles, and quantitatively, by plotting load displacement response of the specimen at different loading phases. The application of the model to anisotropic materials is demonstrated by analyzing the macroscopic response of a fiber-reinforced elastomeric composite. Parametric studies are conducted to understand the effect of different variables on the overall response. A quantitative validation is conducted with existing numerical results. The proposed formulation is then adopted to understand the fracture response of the microstructure of natural rubber reinforced with carbon black particles, and (d) soft tissues such as brain.

2 Theoretical formulation

2.1 Energy functional

Consider a cracked solid $\Omega_0 \in \mathbb{R}^3$ at time t_0 , which can be referred to as reference/undeformed configuration with material points $\mathbf{X} \in \Omega_0$ as shown in Figure 2. The current/deformed configuration of the body at time t is denoted by $\Omega_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$ with spatial points $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_t$. The solid has reinforcements represented by orientation vectors, denoted as \mathbf{a}_0 and \mathbf{a} in the reference and current configuration, respectively. The boundary in the reference configuration $\partial\Omega_0$ is split into disjoint parts $\partial\Omega_{0,u}$ and $\partial\Omega_{0,t_0}$, where the boundary conditions are described as

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \quad \text{on} \quad \partial\Omega_{0,u} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{N} = \bar{\mathbf{t}}_0 \quad \text{on} \quad \partial\Omega_{0,t_0} \quad (1)$$

The deformation between reference placements, \mathbf{X} , and spatial positions, \mathbf{x} , can be mathematically described by the nonlinear deformation map $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ as $\mathbf{x} = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{X}, t)$. The deformation gradient is defined as $\mathbf{F} = \nabla_0 \boldsymbol{\varphi}(\mathbf{X}, t)$, where ∇_0 represents the gradient operator with respect to \mathbf{X} . The volume ratio is defined as $J = \det \mathbf{F}$. For measures of strain, the right and left Cauchy–Green tensors are defined as $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}$ and $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T$, respectively.

Figure 2: (a) Reference configuration Ω_0 at time t_0 and (b) Current configuration Ω_t at time t .

Figure 3: (a) Sharp crack in an anisotropic body and (b) Diffused crack in an anisotropic body.

When the solid body Ω_0 is incompressible or nearly incompressible, distinct volumetric and deviatoric contributions of the deformation gradient have to be considered. The deformation gradient and the right Cauchy–Green tensor can be decomposed as,

$$\mathbf{F} = [J^{1/3} \mathbf{I}] \cdot \bar{\mathbf{F}} \text{ and } \mathbf{C} = [J^{2/3} \mathbf{I}] \cdot \bar{\mathbf{C}} \quad (2)$$

where, $J^{1/3} \mathbf{I}$ and $J^{2/3} \mathbf{I}$ are the volumetric contributions whereas $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$ are the deviatoric contributions.

A sharp crack represented by Γ_0 is diffused to a regularized crack Γ_ϕ over a regularized width l_ϕ . Here ϕ is the phase field order parameter represented by an exponential function $\phi(\mathbf{X}) = e^{-|\mathbf{X}-\mathbf{X}_0 \cdot \mathbf{N}|/l_\phi}$, which is appropriately and naturally bounded by $0 < \phi \leq 1$. \mathbf{X}_0 are points on Γ_0 and \mathbf{N} is the normal to Γ_0 . The limiting cases of the order parameter are $\phi = 0$, and $\phi = 1$, which represent the intact and fully damaged states, respectively. The sharp and regularized descriptions of the crack are shown in Figure 3. The material is anisotropic in nature due to the presence of reinforcements, like fibers in composites, and axons in brain tissue. Therefore, the anisotropic regularized crack surface $\Gamma_\phi(\phi)$ depends on the orientation of the reinforcement as

$$\Gamma_\phi(\phi) = \int_{\Omega_0} \gamma_0(\phi, \nabla_0 \phi; \mathbf{B}) d\Omega_0 \text{ with } \gamma(\phi, \nabla_0 \phi; \mathbf{B}) = \frac{1}{2l_\phi} [\phi^2 + l_\phi^2 \nabla_0 \phi \cdot \mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla_0 \phi] \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{B} := \mathbf{I} + \beta \mathbf{L}$ is a second-order structural tensor with $\mathbf{L} := \mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0$ and β representing the strength of anisotropy. The total energy functional of the fractured material can be written as

$$\mathbb{E} = \int_{\Omega_0} g(\phi) \Psi d\Omega_0 + \int_{\Omega_0} G_c \gamma(\phi, \nabla_0 \phi; \mathbf{B}) d\Omega_0 - \int_{\Omega_0} \bar{\mathbf{b}}_0 \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega_0 - \int_{\partial\Omega_0, t_0} \bar{\mathbf{t}}_0 \cdot \mathbf{u} dA \quad (4)$$

where Ψ represents the strain energy density function, $g(\phi) = [1 - \phi]^2$ is the degradation function, and G_c is the fracture toughness of the material. Finally, $\bar{\mathbf{b}}_0$, $\bar{\mathbf{t}}_0$ are the applied body force and surface traction, respectively. Distinct contributions of matrix (isotropic) and reinforcement (anisotropic) are considered in the strain energy density function. The isotropic contribution can again be split into volumetric and deviatoric contributions to the energy density as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi &= \Psi_{\text{iso}} + \Psi_{\text{ani}}, \quad \Psi_{\text{iso}} = \Psi_v + \Psi_d \\ \Psi(J, \bar{\mathbf{C}}; \mathbf{L}) &= \Psi_v(J) + \Psi_d(\bar{\mathbf{C}}) + \Psi_{\text{ani}}(\mathbf{C}; \mathbf{L}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\Psi(J, \bar{\mathbf{C}}; \mathbf{L}) = \underbrace{\frac{\kappa}{2} [J - 1]^2}_{\Psi_v} + \underbrace{\frac{\mu}{2} [\text{tr } \bar{\mathbf{C}} - 3]}_{\Psi_d} + \underbrace{\frac{k_1}{k_2} [\exp(k_2 \langle \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{L} - 1 \rangle) - 1] - k_1 \langle \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{L} - 1 \rangle}_{\Psi_{\text{ani}}}$$

where κ and μ are the Lamé constants which represent the bulk modulus and shear modulus of the matrix material, respectively, and k_1 and k_2 represent the stiffness and exponent of the reinforcement. Finally, $\langle w \rangle$ denotes the Macauley's function of ' w '.

Remark: The anisotropic strain energy function can be alternatively postulated in terms of fiber properties κ^F , and μ^F , and fiber orientation vector \mathbf{a}_0 as

$$\Psi_{\text{ani}} = \frac{\kappa^F}{2} [\mathbf{E} : \mathbf{L}]^2 + \mu^F [(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}) : \mathbf{L}] \quad \text{with } \mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{I}]$$

The above function has been adopted to model fracture in fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites in [9]. A similar function is adopted in [61] for modeling mode I, mode II and mixed mode bending of unidirectional CFRP, where the energy function is taken as

$$\Psi_{\text{ani}} = \frac{\mu^F}{4} [\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a} - 1]^2 \quad \text{with } \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{a}_0$$

□

From the strain energy function in Eq.(5), the Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor, \mathbf{S} , can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{S} := 2 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{S}_v + \mathbf{S}_d + \mathbf{S}_{\text{ani}} \quad (6)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S}_v &= 2 \frac{\partial \Psi_v}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = 2 \frac{d\Psi_v}{dJ} \frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = 2\kappa [J - 1] \frac{1}{2} J \mathbf{C}^{-1} = \kappa J [J - 1] \mathbf{C}^{-1} \\ \mathbf{S}_d &= 2 \frac{\partial \Psi_d}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \mu \frac{\partial \text{tr } \bar{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \mu [\det \mathbf{C}]^{-1/3} \left[\mathbf{I} - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr } \mathbf{C} \mathbf{C}^{-1} \right] \\ \mathbf{S}_{\text{ani}} &= 2 \frac{\partial \Psi_{\text{ani}}}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = 2k_1 \mathbf{L} [\exp(k_2 \langle \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{L} - 1 \rangle) - 1] \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the Lagrangian elasticity tensor can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{A} &= 2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = 2\mu \det \mathbf{C}^{-1/3} \left[\frac{1}{3} \text{tr } \mathbf{C} \mathbb{I} - \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{C}^{-1} - \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{C}^{-1} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{9} \text{tr } \mathbf{C} \mathbf{C}^{-1} \otimes \mathbf{C}^{-1} \right] \\ &\quad + \kappa J [J - 1] [\mathbf{C}^{-1} \otimes \mathbf{C}^{-1} - 2\mathbb{I}] + \kappa J^2 \mathbf{C}^{-1} \otimes \mathbf{C}^{-1} + 4k_1 k_2 \mathbf{L} \otimes \mathbf{L} \exp(k_2 \langle \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{L} - 1 \rangle) \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{I} and \mathbb{I} are the second-order unit tensor and the fourth-order tensor based on \mathbf{C}^{-1} with cartesian coefficients:

$$(\mathbb{I})_{IJKL} = \frac{1}{2} [(\mathbf{C}^{-1})_{IK} (\mathbf{C}^{-1})_{JL} + (\mathbf{C}^{-1})_{IL} (\mathbf{C}^{-1})_{JK}]$$

Furthermore, a tension-compression decomposition of the strain energy is adopted to avoid fracture under compression[7]. The anisotropic contribution is active only under tension($\mathbf{C} : \mathbf{L} > 1$). Thus, $\Psi_{\text{ani}} = \Psi_{\text{ani}}^+$. Therefore, the decomposition has to be considered only for the matrix material.

$$\Psi = \Psi^+ + \Psi^-; \Psi^+ = \Psi_v^+ + \Psi_d^+ + \Psi_{\text{ani}} \quad \text{with } \Psi^- = \Psi_v^- + \Psi_d^- \quad (8)$$

The deviatoric right Cauchy–Green tensor can be written in terms of its eigen values, $\bar{\lambda}_i$ (isochoric principal stretches), and eigen-vectors, α_i as, $\bar{\mathbf{C}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \bar{\lambda}_i^2 \alpha_i \otimes \alpha_i$. The positive and negative parts of Ψ_v and Ψ_d can now be written as

$$\Psi_v^+ = \frac{\kappa}{2} [J - 1]^2 |_{J>1}, \quad \Psi_d^+ = \frac{\mu}{2} \sum_{\bar{\lambda}_i > 1} [\bar{\lambda}_i^2 - 3], \quad \Psi_v^- = \frac{\kappa}{2} [J - 1]^2 |_{J<1}, \quad \Psi_d^- = \frac{\mu}{2} \sum_{\bar{\lambda}_i < 1} [\bar{\lambda}_i^2 - 3]$$

After considering the additional tension-compression decomposition, the total energy functional in Eq. (4) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbb{E} = \int_{\Omega_0} g(\phi) \Psi^+ d\Omega_0 + \int_{\Omega_0} \Psi^- d\Omega_0 + \int_{\Omega_0} G_c \gamma(\phi, \nabla_0 \phi; \mathbf{B}) d\Omega_0 - \int_{\Omega_0} \bar{\mathbf{b}}_0 \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega_0 - \int_{\partial\Omega_0, t_0} \bar{\mathbf{t}}_0 \cdot \mathbf{u} dA \quad (9)$$

The equilibrium equation and the evolution equation can be obtained from the minimization of Eq. (9) with respect to the displacement \mathbf{u} and the phase field parameter ϕ as

$$\nabla_0 \cdot \mathbf{P} + \bar{\mathbf{b}}_0 = \mathbf{0} \text{ in } \Omega_0 \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{S} \quad (10)$$

$$g'(\phi) \left[\frac{\Psi^+}{G_c} \right] + \left[\frac{1}{l_\phi} [\phi - l_\phi^2 \nabla_0 \cdot (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla_0 \phi)] \right] \geq \theta \text{ in } \Omega_0 \quad (11)$$

with the Neumann type boundary conditions

$$\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{N} = \bar{\mathbf{t}}_0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega_{0,t_0} \text{ and } [\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla_0 \phi] \cdot \mathbf{N} = \theta \text{ on } \partial\Omega_0$$

Here, \mathbf{P} represents the Piola stress, a two-point tensor. Note that Eq. (11) appears as the corresponding Euler equation divided by G_c .

Next, for a composite material, the fracture toughness G_c has two parts corresponding to matrix, G_c^{iso} , and fibers, G_c^{ani} . Furthermore, G_{cI}^{iso} and G_{cII}^{iso} denote the mode I and mode II critical energy release rates of the matrix material in the composite. Accordingly, Eq. (11) is reformulated as

$$g'(\phi) \left[\frac{\Psi_v^+}{G_{cI}^{\text{iso}}} + \frac{\Psi_d^+}{G_{cII}^{\text{iso}}} + \frac{\Psi_{\text{ani}}}{G_c^{\text{ani}}} \right] + \left[\frac{1}{l_\phi} [\phi - l_\phi^2 \nabla_0 \cdot (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla_0 \phi)] \right] \geq \theta \text{ in } \Omega_0 \quad (12)$$

Finally, to model mixed-mode fracture, Eq. (12) is further modified based on a power law criterion adopted in [60] as

$$g'(\phi) \left[\left(\frac{\Psi_v^+}{G_{cI}^{\text{iso}}} \right)^p + \left(\frac{\Psi_d^+}{G_{cII}^{\text{iso}}} \right)^q + \left(\frac{\Psi_{\text{ani}}}{G_c^{\text{ani}}} \right)^r \right] + \left[\frac{1}{l_\phi} [\phi - l_\phi^2 \nabla_0 \cdot (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla_0 \phi)] \right] \geq \theta \text{ in } \Omega_0 \quad (13)$$

Here, p , q , and r are the exponents that control the effect of different energies on the crack propagation. The weak forms of equations (10), and (13) can eventually be written as

$$\int_{\Omega_0} \mathbf{P} : \nabla_0 \delta \mathbf{u} \, d\Omega_0 = \int_{\Omega_0} \bar{\mathbf{b}}_0 \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} \, d\Omega_0 + \int_{\partial\Omega_{0,t_0}} \bar{\mathbf{t}}_0 \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} \, dA \quad (14)$$

$$\int_{\Omega_0} \left[[g'(\phi)\mathcal{H}] \delta\phi + \left[\frac{1}{l_\phi} [\phi \delta\phi + [l_\phi^2 \nabla_0 \phi \cdot \mathbf{B}] \cdot \nabla \delta\phi] \right] \right] d\Omega_0 \geq \theta, \quad (15)$$

where we use the abbreviation

$$\mathcal{H} = \left(\frac{\Psi_v^+}{G_{cI}^{\text{iso}}} \right)^p + \left(\frac{\Psi_d^+}{G_{cII}^{\text{iso}}} \right)^q + \left(\frac{\Psi_{\text{ani}}}{G_c^{\text{ani}}} \right)^r \quad (16)$$

2.2 Finite element approximations

For the here considered two-dimensional case, a continuum body is discretized into three-noded triangular finite elements. The displacement field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t)$ and the phase field $\phi(\mathbf{X}, t)$ for all nodes N can be approximated using shape functions $N_I(\mathbf{X})$ and nodal values \mathbf{w}_I of the displacement field and $w_{\phi I}$ of the phase field as

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t) \approx \sum_{I=1}^N \mathbf{w}_I(t) N_I(\mathbf{X}) \quad \text{and} \quad \phi(\mathbf{X}, t) \approx \sum_{I=1}^N w_{\phi I}(t) N_I(\mathbf{X}) \quad (17)$$

The gradients of the displacements and the phase field can be approximated as

$$\nabla_0 \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t) \approx \sum_{I=1}^N \mathbf{w}_I(t) \otimes \nabla_0 N_I(\mathbf{X}) \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla_0 \phi(\mathbf{X}, t) \approx \sum_{I=1}^N w_{\phi I}(t) \nabla_0 N_I(\mathbf{X}) \quad (18)$$

The discrete residual for the Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) can be written as

$$\mathbf{R}_I^u = \int_{\Omega_0} \bar{\mathbf{b}}_0 N_I d\Omega_0 + \int_{\partial\Omega_{0,t_0}} \bar{\mathbf{t}}_0 N_I dA - \int_{\Omega_0} \mathbf{P} \cdot \nabla_0 N_I d\Omega_0 = \mathbf{0} \quad (19)$$

$$R_I^\phi = - \int_{\Omega_0} \left[\left[g'(\phi) \mathcal{H} + \frac{\phi}{l_\phi} \right] N_I + [l_\phi \nabla_0 \phi \cdot \mathbf{B}] \cdot \nabla_0 N_I \right] d\Omega_0 \leq 0 \quad (20)$$

An incremental iterative solution strategy based on the Newton–Raphson method reads as

$$\mathbf{R}_I^{u(k+1)} = \mathbf{R}_I^{u(k)} + d\mathbf{R}_I^u = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{with} \quad d\mathbf{R}_I^u = \sum_{J=1}^N \mathbf{K}_{IJ}^u \cdot d\mathbf{w}_J \quad (21)$$

$$R_I^{\phi(k+1)} = R_I^{\phi(k)} + dR_I^\phi = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad dR_I^\phi = \sum_{J=1}^N K_{IJ}^\phi dw_{\phi J} \quad (22)$$

The component matrices of the global tangent stiffness matrix are given by

$$\mathbf{K}_{IJ}^u = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_I^u}{\partial \mathbf{w}_J} = \int_{\Omega_0} [\partial_{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{P} \cdot \nabla_0 N_I] \cdot \nabla_0 N_J d\Omega_0 \quad (23)$$

$$K_{IJ}^\phi = \frac{\partial R_I^\phi}{\partial w_{\phi J}} = \int_{\Omega_0} \left[g''(\phi) \mathcal{H} + \frac{1}{l_\phi} \right] N_I N_J d\Omega_0 + \int_{\Omega_0} [l_\phi \mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla_0 N_I] \cdot \nabla_0 N_J d\Omega_0 \quad (24)$$

3 Numerical examples

The proposed phase field model is first validated with experimental results by conducting mixed-mode fracture tests on thin elastomer sheets. A second validation example is performed on a unidirectional fiber-reinforced elastomeric composite. The obtained results are correlated with numerical results from literature. The performance of the present model is furthermore demonstrated through the following examples : (i) Mode I loading of double edge notched specimens of carbon black reinforced natural rubber, and (ii) Response of brain tissue at the cellular level, having axons at different orientations subjected to different modes of loading. Linear triangular elements are adopted in the numerical analysis using the finite element method. A displacement control approach is adopted for the solution algorithm. For numerical convenience, all the examples have been performed in 2D based on MATLAB codes developed for 2D plane strain finite element analysis. At each loading step, the displacement and the crack phase are solved using a staggered approach.

3.1 Mixed-mode fracture test on thin elastomer sheets

Figure 4: Geometry and boundary conditions for mixed-mode fracture test.

To validate the proposed mixed-mode formulation, a specimen of a silicone elastomer sheet having an initial crack at an angle θ is considered. The geometry and boundary conditions are shown in Figure 4. To study the crack propagation under different degrees of mode mixity, three different crack orientations, namely, $\theta = 0^\circ, \theta = 30^\circ, \theta = 60^\circ$ are considered for the analysis. The elastomers behave elastically under large deformations and can be considered as a hyperelastic material, whose properties are taken as, $\mu = 21.4$ kPa, $\kappa = 14.25$ kPa, $G_{cI} = 0.154$ N/mm. These values are taken from the experimental paper [62]. To model the crack propagation under mixed-mode loading, the mixed-mode fracture criterion given in Eq. (13) is adopted for this example and the parameters are set to $p = 1.6$, $q = r = 1.0$, $G_{cII}/G_{cI} = 0.5$. The values of p, q, r are taken from [60], where parametric studies are conducted and it is concluded that, for this combination of p, q, r , the relative error between the numerical and experimental findings is minimized.

Figure 5: Numerical and experimental results of crack propagation for mixed-mode fracture test for $\theta = 0^\circ$ corresponding to (a) **1**, (b) **3**, (c) **4** in load-deflection curve plotted from [62], and (d) **1**, (e) **2**, and (f) **3** in load-deflection curve obtained from the present formulation.

Figure 6: Numerical and experimental results of crack propagation for mixed-mode fracture test for $\theta = 30^\circ$ corresponding to (a) **1**, (b) **3**, (c) **4** in load-deflection curve plotted from [62], and (d) **1**, (e) **2**, and (f) **3** in load-deflection curve obtained from the present formulation.

Figure 7: Numerical and experimental results of crack propagation for mixed-mode fracture test for $\theta = 60^\circ$ corresponding to (a) **1**, (b) **3**, (c) **4** in load-deflection curve plotted from [62], and (d) **1**, (e) **2**, and (f) **3** in load-deflection curve obtained from the present formulation.

Figure 8: Numerical and experimental load displacement response for mixed-mode fracture test for (a) $\theta = 60^\circ$, (b) $\theta = 30^\circ$, and (c) $\theta = 0^\circ$.

The crack propagation obtained using the present formulation for $\theta = 0^\circ, \theta = 30^\circ, \theta = 60^\circ$ at various displacements are depicted in Figure 5, Figure 6, and Figure 7, respectively. For the crack orientation, $\theta = 0^\circ$, the crack propagates straight, similar to the standard case of a specimen subjected to mode I loading. For the crack orientations, $\theta = 30^\circ, 60^\circ$, with the increase in the vertical displacement, the crack opens asymmetrically about the initial crack orientation, and then takes a curved path which is an indication that the specimen is subjected to mixed-mode loading. As the specimens undergo large deformations, the crack tip becomes blunted. The results are compared with the experimental images of crack propagation reported in [62]. From Figures 5 - 7, it can be observed that the crack trajectory is similar to the experimental findings. The load displacement response for

different values of θ is plotted along with experimental values in Figure 8. The failure load increases with an increase in the crack angle.

3.2 Anisotropic single edge notched specimen

Figure 9: Geometry and boundary conditions of anisotropic single edge notched specimen.

The proposed anisotropic hyperelastic formulation has been adopted to model the fracture in a fiber-reinforced elastomeric composite with fibers oriented at different orientations. Parametric studies are conducted to understand the effect of fiber orientation θ and anisotropy parameter β on the crack propagation and mechanical response of the composite under large deformations. We consider a 1 units \times 1 units specimen with a notch extending to half of the specimen as shown in Figure 9. The load is applied in terms of displacement \bar{u} at the top and bottom edges. Lamé constants are taken as $\kappa = 121.15$ GPa, $\mu = 80.77$ GPa. The fracture toughness for matrix G_c^{iso} and fibers G_c^{ani} are considered to be 0.0027 kN/mm. The fiber material properties k_1 and k_2 are taken as 0 and 1 respectively [7].

Figure 10: Crack propagation of anisotropic single edge notched specimen for (a) $\theta = 15^\circ, \beta = 50$, (b) $\theta = 30^\circ, \beta = 50$, (c) $\theta = 45^\circ, \beta = 50$, (d) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 0$, (e) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 25$, (f) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 50$.

Figure 11: Load displacement plots of anisotropic single edge notched specimen for (a) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 0$, (b) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 0$ [7], (c) $\theta = 15^\circ, \beta = 50$, (d) $\theta = 30^\circ, \beta = 50$, (e) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 25$, (f) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 25$ [7], (g) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 50$, (h) $\theta = 40^\circ, \beta = 50$ [7], and (i) $\theta = 45^\circ, \beta = 50$.

As a first study, three fiber orientations $\theta = 15^\circ, \theta = 30^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$ are considered for a constant anisotropy parameter value of $\beta = 50$. The evolution of the crack for the three fiber orientations is shown in Figure 10 (a)-(c). It can be observed that the crack path is along the fiber direction which is also observed from experiments [63]. The next study is to understand the effect of the anisotropy parameter β , for which three cases are considered by taking $\beta = 0, \beta = 25$, and $\beta = 50$ for $\theta = 40^\circ$. From Figure 10 (d)-(f), it can be inferred that for $\beta = 0$ which represents the isotropic case, the crack does not follow the fiber direction and propagates perpendicular to the loading. As the β value increases from 25 to 50, the crack is aligned more along the fiber direction ($\theta = 40^\circ$). The load displacement values for all the cases are plotted in Figure 11 and compared with the results from the literature [7]. Therefore, the present model can be adopted for modeling fracture in fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites. From Figure 11, it can be inferred that the failure load increases with an increase in the value of the anisotropy parameter and the fiber orientation.

3.3 Double edge notched specimen of carbon black reinforced natural rubber

The aim of the present study is to understand the mechanical and fracture response of a natural rubber reinforced with carbon black particles under mode I loading. For this purpose, the microstructure of the composite is subjected to uniform vertical displacement at the top and bottom edges as shown in Figure 12. The analysis is carried out for different values of initial notch length, b , and volume fraction of carbon particles, v_f . A perfect bonding between carbon particles and natural rubber is assumed. For the first study, the volume fraction is taken as $v_f = 0.3$ ($r = 0.219$ mm), and the notch length b is varied, $b = 0.1$ mm, $b = 0.15$ mm and $b = 0.2$ mm. For the second study, the notch length is kept constant as $b = 0.1$ mm and the volume fraction is varied as $v_f = 0.25$ ($r = 0.199$ mm), $v_f = 0.3$ ($r = 0.219$ mm) and $v_f = 0.35$ ($r = 0.236$ mm). The material properties are taken as follows: for rubber, $E = 13.5$ MPa, $\nu = 0.45$, and for carbon black particles, $E = 1350$ MPa, $\nu = 0.3$. $G_c = 0.28$ N/mm [64]. E and ν represent the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio respectively.

Figure 12: Geometry and boundary conditions of double edge notched carbon black reinforced natural rubber specimen.

Figure 13: Failure of double edge notched carbon black reinforced natural rubber specimen for (a) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.1$, (b) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.15$, (c) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.2$, (d) $v_f = 0.25, b = 0.1$, (e) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.1$, (f) $v_f = 0.35, b = 0.1$.

The failure of carbon black reinforced natural rubber for all the cases is depicted in Figure 13. It is observed that, with the increase in the load, the two notches open symmetrically, and voids are initiated at the area above and below the central fiber. The void below the central carbon particle continues to propagate and results in complete failure of the specimen. The results obtained are in accordance with those reported in [64]. The load displacement values are plotted in Figure 14. From the figure, it is evident that, for a fixed volume fraction, v_f , as the notch length b increases, the failure strain remains unchanged but a slight decrease is observed in peak load. With the increase in volume fraction, v_f , the failure strain and the peak load decreases.

Figure 14: Load displacement plots of double edge notched carbon black reinforced natural rubber specimen for (a) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.1$, (b) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.15$, (c) $v_f = 0.3, b = 0.2$, (d) $v_f = 0.25, b = 0.1$, and (e) $v_f = 0.35, b = 0.1$.

3.4 Response of axons under different modes of loading

Figure 15: Geometry and boundary conditions of the brain specimen.

Diffuse axonal injury (DAI) is a type of traumatic brain injury (TBI) that occurs when the axons are sheared due to accident-impact-induced brain movement. Understanding the response of axons under different modes of mechanical loading may help in assessing the probability of brain injury, and the occurrence of DAI. A specimen of brain tissue at cellular level having axons at different orientations θ subjected to different modes of loading is considered for the analysis. The geometry and boundary conditions are depicted in Figure 15. ζ represent the loading angle with respect to the global \mathbf{X} axis.

Six cases are considered for the analysis, namely, (a) $\zeta = 0^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\zeta = 30^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (c) $\zeta = 45^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (d) $\zeta = 0^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$, (e) $\zeta = 30^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$, and (f) $\zeta = 45^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$. The material properties are taken from [34], where the bulk modulus and shear modulus are taken as 2.7 GPa and 12.7 Pa respectively. The fracture toughness is taken as 0.0027 kN/mm. The values of k_1 and k_2 are considered to be 121.2 Pa and 1.

Figure 16: Plots of equivalent stress σ_{eq} for (a) $\zeta = 0^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\zeta = 30^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (c) $\zeta = 45^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (d) $\zeta = 0^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$, (e) $\zeta = 30^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$, and (f) $\zeta = 45^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$ at $\bar{u} = 37.5\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 17: Plots of axonal strain, $E_{\theta\theta}$ for (a) $\zeta = 0^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\zeta = 30^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (c) $\zeta = 45^\circ, \theta = 0^\circ$, (d) $\zeta = 0^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$, (e) $\zeta = 30^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$, and (f) $\zeta = 45^\circ, \theta = 45^\circ$ at $\bar{u} = 37.5\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 18: Plots of crack phase field ϕ for (a) $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, (c) $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, (d) $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$, (e) $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$, and (f) $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$ at $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = 37.5\mu\text{m}$.

The equivalent stress is evaluated as $\sigma_{\text{eq}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{dev}} : \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{dev}}}$ for the analysis, whereby $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{dev}}$ represent the deviatoric part of the Cauchy stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$. The axonal strain, $E_{\theta\theta}$, follows as

$$E_{\theta\theta} = \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{a}_0 \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{a}_0 = \cos \theta \mathbf{E}_1 + \sin \theta \mathbf{E}_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{I}].$$

Figure 19: Load displacement plots for (a) $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, (b) $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, (c) $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, (d) $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$, (e) $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$, and (f) $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$.

The equivalent stress, σ_{eq} , axonal strain, $E_{\theta\theta}$, and crack phase field, ϕ plots are shown in Figure 16 - 18 respectively. From Figure 16, it is observed that the equivalent stress is pronounced at the centre and at the inclined edges of the deformed configuration. The value of σ_{eq} is high for, $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$ and low for, $\zeta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$. From Figure 17, it can be observed that a higher value of axonal strain

is observed for $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 45^\circ$ and a lower value for $\zeta = 45^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$. The crack phase field values ϕ for all the six cases are plotted in Figure 18. Except for $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, for all the remaining cases the fracture is initiated at the inclined edges of the specimen. For $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, the fracture initiates at the center.

To summarize, failure due to stretching is observed for $\zeta = 0^\circ$, $\theta = 0^\circ$, and for other modes of loading, the failure is due to shearing of axons. The load displacement values for all the cases are plotted in Figure 19. From the figure, it can be observed that for a fixed value of θ , as ζ increases, the failure load decreases, and for a fixed value of ζ , as θ increases, the failure load also increases. For $\theta = 0^\circ$, a linear load-displacement response is seen, and for $\theta = 45^\circ$, nonlinear response is observed. For loading angle, $\zeta = 0$, a higher failure load is observed for fiber orientation $\theta = 0^\circ$, and for $\zeta = 45$, a higher failure load is observed for fiber orientation $\theta = 45^\circ$.

4 Conclusions

In this work, a unified phase field method to model anisotropic mixed-mode fracture in hyperelastic materials is presented. The formulation considers the following, (a) a volumetric-deviatoric decomposition in the strain energy density function to capture the role of different parts of energy in driving tensile and shear cracks under complex loading paths, (b) a tension-compression decomposition in the strain energy density function to ensure the cracking to occur only under tension, (c) an exponential anisotropic strain energy density function depending on the orientation of reinforcements, like, fiber in fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites and axons in brain tissue, and (d) a mixed-mode crack driving force based on a power law to model the mixed-mode fracture evident in elastomers. The proposed unification is validated through numerical examples on (i) silicone elastomers, and (ii) unidirectional fiber-reinforced elastomeric composites. The performance of the model is furthermore illustrated through simulations on (iii) natural rubber reinforced with carbon black particles, and (iv) brain tissue at the cellular level reinforced with axons. The highlights of the present work are, (a) the mixed-mode fracture criterion is validated by considering an inclined crack in a soft silicone elastomer subjected to vertical displacement at the top and restrained at the bottom, to ensure the crack tip is under mixed-mode loading locally. A curved crack trajectory is observed which is in good agreement with the experimental findings, (b) the influence of fiber orientation, θ , and the anisotropy parameter, β , is examined by analyzing a unidirectional fiber-reinforced elastomeric composite lamina, (c) the interaction of the crack path with the microstructure of a carbon black reinforced natural rubber is studied, and (d) the response of brain tissue is studied under different loading conditions by computing the equivalent stress, axonal strain, and damage profiles. The proposed formulation combines the advantages of different decompositions of strain energy, and a driving force based on a mixed-mode fracture criterion. The present formulation can be applied to model mixed-mode delamination in elastomeric composites, as well as mixed-mode crack propagation in generic soft materials and for interfaces between two dissimilar materials under large deformations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

D. Pranavi: Data curation, Writing - original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Software, Validation. **A. Rajagopal:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **P. Steinmann:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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